

Exceptions to the Rule? Ethnographic Alternatives to Cumulative Cultural Evolution

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Key concepts: anarchic theory in ethnography and archaeology; cultural heterochrony; cumulative/subtractive cultural evolution; immediate-return/egalitarian hunters-gatherers; ratcheting/leveling mechanisms.

